

REACTION BETWEEN GLUCOSE AND IODINE IN ALKALINE MEDIUM. EFFECT OF NEUTRAL SALTS.

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The iodometric process for the estimation of reducing sugars has been examined by a number of investigators, the chief of these being Rouijn (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1897, **36**, 349), Bougault (*Compt. rend.*, 1917, **164**, 1008), Willstätter and Schudel (*Ber.*, 1918, **51**, 780), Judd (*Biochem. J.*, 1920, **14**, 255), Baker and Hulton (*Biochem. J.*, 1920, **14**, 754), Cajori (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1922, **84**, 617), Kolthoff (*Z. Untersuch. nehr. Genussm.*, 1923, **45**, 131, 141), Hinton and Macara (*Analyst*, 1924, **49**, 2), and Gobel (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1927, **72**, 801). They investigated the oxidation of glucose by iodine in the presence of either borax, sodium carbonate, or caustic soda for particular purposes. Allen and Winegarden (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1923, **58**, 225) studied the rate of oxidation of glucose by iodine in presence of insulin. Kappanna (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 387) studied the effect of phosphates and p_H on the reaction between dextrose and iodine.

The effect of the following neutral salts, *viz.*, chlorides, bromides and nitrates of sodium, ammonium and potassium and potassium iodide has been studied on this reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL.

N/₁₀-Iodine solution (50 c.c.), *M*/₂₀-glucose solution (50 c.c.), *N*/₂₀-NaOH solution (20 c.c.), required amount of the neutral salt solution and distilled water to keep the volume constant, were taken together in a stoppered bottle using a thermostat at 30°. After allowing the mixture to stand for 40 minutes, 10 c.c. of this reaction mixture were taken out in a conical flask containing 25 c.c. of about *N*/₈₀-Na₂S₂O₃ solution. The solution was then acidified with 5 c.c. of semi-normal H₂SO₄ and the excess of thio-sulphate was immediately titrated back against about *N*/₄₀₀-iodine solution with starch as indicator. In this way a number of readings were taken using three concentrations of the neutral salts.

TABLE I.
Temp. = 30°.

Salt soln. added.	K salts (× 10 ⁵).			Na salts (× 10 ⁵).			Ammon. salts (× 10 ⁵).		
	KCl.	KBr.	KNO ₃ .	NaCl.	NaBr.	NaNO ₃ .	NH ₄ Cl.	NH ₄ Br.	NH ₄ NO ₃ .
0 c.c.	4·638	4·638	4·638	4·638	4·638	4·638	4·638	4·638	4·638
5	4·380	4·420	4·420	4·200	4·210	4·330	3·930	4·160	4·350
10	3·875	4·056	4·270	3·860	3·900	4·100	3·530	3·530	3·866
20	3·341	3·630	3·860	3·124	3·467	3·730	2·857	3·215	3·630

DISCUSSION.

From Table I, it is concluded that by adding neutral salts, *vis.*, chlorides, bromides and nitrates of potassium, sodium and ammonium, the speed of the oxidation of glucose by iodine is retarded, and the velocity constant of the reaction decreases with increasing concentration of the salts. The variation in the velocity constant with these different salts show that the value of K for a given concentration of the salt is not independent of the nature of the added salt.

The comparative results of all salts are summarised in the following table.

TABLE II.

Salts.	Salt soln. added at 30° = 20 c.c.		
	Chloride	Bromide.	Nitrate.
Potassium	3.341×10^{-5}	3.630×10^{-5}	3.860×10^{-5}
Sodium	3.124	3.467	3.730
Ammonium	2.857	3.215	3.630

Table II shows that the oxidation of glucose by sodium hypoiodite is retarded in the order given below.

The decrease in the velocity constant can be attributed to the formation of complex ions between iodine and halide ions. This may be due to the fact that there the number of free ions becomes less, and complex iodine ions as in the case of potassium iodide ($\text{KI} + \text{I}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{KI}_3$) predominate. Where no such formation of complex takes place as in the case of nitrates, the velocity constant is hardly affected. The case of ammonium nitrate is an exception which shows that iodine forms some complex ions with ammonia as is well known, and also when ammonium salts are added the diminution in velocity may be due to diminution of p_H due to reaction between NH_4' and OH' of NaOH . Thus it may be assumed that the free iodine ions are active in the reaction.